

SoftHand Pro: a Robust and Adaptive Bionic Hand to Enable Physical Interaction

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Abstract—The loss of an upper limb is a major trauma which affects both the personal and the social dimensions of an individual, only solutions capable to properly balance functional and structural anthropomorphism can really restore the quality of life of people with limb loss. Nowadays, state of the art of prosthetic hands is divided between very simple hook-like systems, and more advanced solutions, that try to match the functions of human hand at the cost of severe lack in intuitiveness and reliability. In this talk we present the last evolution of the SoftHand Pro, a soft multi-digit prosthetic hand in which structural and functional anthropomorphism are obtained thanks to the fruitful combination of soft robotics technologies and sensory-motor synergies. We introduce the new design and discuss outcomes coming from its use in the context of the Cybathlon Experience 2018, highlighting how a soft and adaptive design help the user in the execution of the proposed daily life activities.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hands represent the main interface of humans with the world which they manipulate and the perceptual tools for sensing the environment. One of the challenges of modern technology is try to replace the structure and functionalities of the human hand in a robotic aids which enable persons with upper limb loss to effectively restore their quality of life. Moreover, the support of a reliable and more natural prosthetic aid can play a critical role in psychological well-being as well as social acceptance. State of art of modern hand prosthesis is rich of advanced prototypes, which usually offer a broader set of movement capabilities, with the possibility to control up to 4 or 5 motors independently, achieving several different postures [1], but unfortunately not so easy to control. This issue often leads on the device abandonment or on the choice to use simpler solutions as body powered hooks [2]. Moreover, these polyarticular myoelectric prosthesis cannot replicate exactly the complex architecture of bones, joints, muscles and ligaments of the human hand. Indeed, to limit the system technical complexity, they inevitably require a loss in terms of number of degrees of freedom and substructures included. In the recent past our group introduced the SoftHand Pro, a soft multi-digit

*This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 under grant agreement No. 688857 (SoftPro). The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the authors. The European Commission or its services cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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Fig. 1. A user holding a phone with the new version of the SoftHand Pro.

prosthetic hand in which structural and functional anthropomorphism are obtained thanks to the fruitful combination of soft robotics technologies and sensory-motor synergies. The resulting system, while still keeping an aesthetically and functional biomimetic design, is capable to perform a useful subset of the functions of human hands. In this talk we present the last evolution of the SoftHand Pro and discuss outcomes coming from its use in the context of the Cybathlon Experience 2018, highlighting how a soft and adaptive design help the user in the execution of daily life activities.

II. THE SOFTHAND PRO

The SoftHand Pro is a 19 DOF anthropomorphic hand that combines intuitiveness, adaptivity and robustness. The shape-morphing artificial hand we propose is the result of a scientifically principled biomimetic combination of soft "muscles", elastic "ligaments", flexible "tendons", articular "joints" and rigid "bones" with kinaesthetic and cutaneous "receptors" inspired by the principles that underpin the human architecture and its sensorymotor apparatus and realized through contemporary technologies such as soft robotics. Thanks to the use of a single motor to activate all the joints in a coordinated "synergistic" fashion, the hand affords qualities such as simple control and adaptability to the grasp pattern. Indeed, the SoftHand Pro can be myoelectrically-controlled using only two surface electromyography (EMG) electrodes. The preliminary prototype of the SoftHand Pro was tested with individuals with limb loss [4] with encouraging results. Recently we developed a new version of the hand, showed in Fig.1. The shape of the hand, and consequently the mechanical and electronic components, were designed in order to obtain a more human-like and smaller shape,

Fig. 2. SoftHand Pro at the Cybathlon Experience 2018. Tasks: (a) Clean Up, (b) Laundry, (c) Home Improvement and (d) Wire Loop.

Fig. 3. The photo-sequence presents our strategy adopted to grasp a mug. The SoftHand Pro can change its shape according with the environmental constraints, and we exploited this feature to get a different closure shape.

TABLE I
RESULTS OF THE SOFTHAND PRO TEAM AT CYBATHLON EXPERIENCE 2018

	Race	Clean Up	Laundry	Home Improvement	Wire Loop	TOTAL SCORE	TOTAL TIME (s)
DAY 1	1	101	104	0	0	205	-
	2	0	104	110	125	339	290
DAY 2	1	0	104	110	125	339	276
	2	101	104	110	125	440	360
DAY 3	1	101	0	0	0	101	89
	2	101	104	110	125	440	323

together with a lighter weight. Moreover, the new release of the SoftHand Pro was provided with a customized cosmetic glove in silicone, to ensure a good and stable grasp.

III. THE CYBATHLON EXPERIENCE: REHACARE 2018

We explored the advantages of our approach in the context of Cybathlon Experience 2018, where we participate as SoftHand Pro team. Our pilot (38, Female) has congenital malformation at the trans-radial level in the left hand. She is an user of cosmetic prostheses, and occasional user of myoelectric prostheses. The four participant teams were asked to compete two times per day. The race consisted in complete four tasks in a maximum time of 6 minutes. The proposed tasks varying from abstract, aimed to challenge different aspects of the Pilot's control and prosthetic technology itself, to practical tasks mimicking ADLs, aimed at testing prosthesis functionality in real-world situations. Some examples are reported in Fig. 2. The results (see Table I) achieved by the SoftHand Pro team are promising and show the potentiality of the system. Only in one race (day 3 - race 1) she was able to complete only the first task because of a device technical problem. In two tracks our pilot was able to complete all the four tasks in less than 6 minutes, highlighting that a proper trade-off between form a function can offer good performance and robustness. Soft-robotics

technologies and the hand adaptability offer the possibility to execute daily living task in a more natural way. Exploiting these features the user is able to perform different grips with unconventional approach, as through imposed constraints. Fig. 3 shows the strategies adopted to grasp and move a mug. The hand resilience plays a key role to perform more work-oriented tasks, as hammering a nail.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank Mattia Poggiani, Manuel Barbarossa and Vinicio Tincani for their invaluable support in designing and building the prototype, and our pilot Maria Fossati.

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